

1 **Molecular function of the human papillomavirus E2 protein.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

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8 The full spectrum of interaction partners and molecular functions of the viral gene products encoded by the papillomaviruses remains unknown. We studied E2 functions and interaction partners in human immortalized keratinocytes. E2 has nuclear functions. We describe here activation of the oncogenic homeobox factor *Tcf19* by HPV E2. A second presumed molecular function of E2 gathered from transcriptomic study of E2-expressing cells was induction of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA synthase 1, encoded by *Hmgcs1*.

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10 Citations

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